

**New data to the Microlepidoptera fauna of Hungary, part XX
(Lepidoptera: Autostichidae, Batrachedridae, Elachistidae,
Sesiidae, Tineidae, Tortricidae)**

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Abstract – The Microlepidoptera species *Batrachedra enormis* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1853) (Batrachedridae), *Cosmiotes exactella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855) (Elachistidae), *Bembecia iberica* Spatenka, 1992 (Sesiidae), *Lichenotinea pustulatella* (Zeller, 1852) (Tineidae), and *Ditula angustiorana* (Haworth, 1811) (Tortricidae) are recorded from Hungary for the first time. Additional records of *Symmoca signatella* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854) (Autostichidae) are also given.

Key words – new records, faunistics

INTRODUCTION

Several microlepidopteran species were recorded as new for the fauna of Hungary in previous parts of this series of papers. The aim of the present paper is to present further five species new to the fauna of Hungary, as well as additional records to a species which was previously known from Hungary based on a single occurrence record. Voucher specimens, unless stated otherwise below, are deposited in the private collection of the author.

RESULTS

Autostichidae

Symmoca signatella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1854)

Material examined – A collecting event was organised in the Soroksár Botanical Garden, Budapest, on 24.VI.2022, for the memory of the late Ottó Merkl (1957–2021). A white sheet was illuminated with a 125W HgL bulb, set up by the author, to present this collecting method to the visitors of the firefly observation tour organised by the staff of the botanical garden. Only a few

moths visited the light in the early evening; however, one specimen of *Symmoca signatella* was found among them. The collecting event was finished at midnight. The author returned to the same locality on 28.VI.2022 to collect additional specimens of this species. At this occasion an all night long collecting resulted in a dozen specimens of *Symmoca signatella*.

Remarks – Prior to this study the species was known from Hungary by a single record from Szigetmonostor (SZABÓKY 2014).

Figs 1–2. *Batrachedra enormis* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1853), 1 = habitus drawing, 2 = living specimen in Budapest, Soroksár, 27.VI.2023 (drawing and photo by Csaba Szabóky)

Batrachedridae

Batrachedra enormis (Herrich-Schäffer, 1853)

(Figs 1–2)

Material examined – On 28.VI.2022, during the author's attempt to collect additional specimens of *Symmoca signatella* in the Soroksár Botanical Garden, Budapest (see above), a relatively large microlepidopteran with lanceolate forewings arrived to the light around midnight. The specimen remained undetermined in the field, and it was later identified by Ignác Richter as *Batrachedra enormis* (gen. prep. 32759). The author returned to the same locality on 27.VI.2023 for another collecting, this time from dusk to dawn. As a result, further three specimens of *Batrachedra enormis* were collected, again around midnight. Another specimen of the species was collected on 20.VIII.2023 in a garden in Csepel (21st District), Budapest, by Balázs Tóth, on a white sheet illuminated by a 160 W HMLI bulb. This specimen is deposited in the Hungarian Natural History Museum (HNHM, Budapest) (specimen No.: HNHM_LEP_11498).

Remarks – First records for Hungary. *Batrachedra enormis* is native to Mexico and the southern United States, and in Europe it has been known only from France (GERMAIN *et al.* 2017); therefore, the Hungarian records also represent the second European report of the species. The caterpillars feed on yucca leaves (*Yucca* spp., Agaveaceae). The species should be placed after the last *Batrachedra* species in the Hungarian checklist (SZABÓKY *et al.* 2002). Proposed Hungarian name: jukka-lándzsásmolylepke.

Elachistidae

Cosmiotes exactella (Herrich-Schäffer, 1855)

Material examined – An unidentified moth was attracted to light at Nyírjes lake, near Sirok, Mátra Mountains (Heves County) on 7.IX.2006. The specimen was identified by Zdenko Tokár as *Cosmiotes exactella* (gen. prep. 10263).

Remarks – First record for Hungary. The species is distributed all over Europe, except Lithuania, Poland, United Kingdom, Ireland, Portugal, Corsica, Sardinia, Sicily, Malta, Bulgaria, Albania and Crete (KARSHOLT & RAZOWSKI 1996). Its host plant is *Poa nemoralis* L. (Poaceae). Two generations are known to develop. The brackets in GOZMÁNY (1955: 8) are to be deleted. Proposed Hungarian name: perjemoly.

Sesiidae
Bembecia iberica Spatenka, 1992
(Fig. 3)

Material examined – Coleopterologist Ottó Merkl regularly collected in the area of Sas Hill, Budapest, by sweeping, resulting also some material of Lepidoptera. On 21.VII.2012 he collected three specimens which were preliminarily identified as *Epermenia pontificella* (Hübner, 1796), *Thyris fenestrella* (Scopoli, 1763), and *Synanthedon vespiformis* (Linnaeus, 1761). Later on, the latter specimen was re-examined and identified by the author as *Bembecia iberica*.

Remarks – First record for Hungary. This species is distributed in Southern Europe (Iberian Peninsula, France including Corsica, and Italy including Sardinia). Its recorded host plants include *Hippocrepis* spp., *Lotus* spp., *Anthyllis vulneraria* L., *Melilotus* spp., and *Tetragonolobus* spp. (all Fabaceae). Identification: antenna yellow with black tip; hind leg yellow, hind tibia black close to spur (LASTŮVKA & LASTŮVKA 2001). Proposed Hungarian name: ibériai szitkár.

Fig. 3. *Bembecia iberica* Spatenka, 1992 (drawing by Csaba Szabóky)

Tineidae

Lichenotinea pustulatella (Zeller, 1852)

(Fig. 4)

Material examined – A portable UV light trap was deployed on the top of Esztramos Hill, Bódvarákó (Borsod-Abaúj-Zemplén County), at the base of a rock wall on 4.VI.2017. The collected material contained a tiny moth specimen, which was later identified as *Lichenotinea pustulatella*.

Remarks – First record for Hungary. The species is widely distributed in Europe (Germany, Belgium, France, Spain, Italy, Switzerland, Austria, countries of the former Yugoslavia, Romania, Bulgaria, Greece) (GAEDIKE 2015). Hosts: lichens on rock surfaces. The brackets in GOZMÁNY & SZŐCS (1965: 157) are to be deleted. Proposed Hungarian name: zuzmófáló moly.

Fig. 4. *Lichenotinea pustulatella* (Zeller, 1852) (drawing by Csaba Szabóky)

Tortricidae

Ditula angustiorana (Haworth, 1811)

(Fig. 5)

Material examined – In Leányfalu (Pest County), at the porch of Gyöngyvirág street 16, the author set up a white sheet, illuminated with a 125W HgL bulb, on 23.IX.2023. The collecting event started at 7 p.m.; it was raining all night, and the temperature was 24 °C. In total, 45 species of Lepidoptera were

attracted to the light, among them a specimen identified by the author as *Ditula angustiorana*. The attempt to collect more specimens of the species in the same locality on 26.IX.2023 remained unsuccessful.

Remarks – First record for Hungary. This species is widely distributed in Europe (Norway, Sweden, Netherlands, United Kingdom, Ireland, Germany, Poland, Belgium, Luxembourg, Spain, Portugal, France (including Corsica), Italy (including Sardinia), Switzerland, Slovenia, Serbia) (KARSHOLT & RAZOWSKI 1996, RAZOWSKI 2002). The caterpillars feed on several species of *Hedera* (Araliaceae), *Ilex* (Aquifoliaceae), *Juniperus* (Cupressaceae), *Larix* (Pinaceae), *Taxus* (Taxaceae), *Laurus* (Lauraceae), *Malus*, *Prunus*, *Pyrus* (all Rosaceae), *Rhododendron* (Ericaceae), *Viscum* (Santalaceae), and *Vitis* (Vitaceae). In the close vicinity (20 m) of the collecting site *Hedera*, *Taxus*, *Laurus*, and *Vitis* were present. Proposed Hungarian name: tiszafa-sodrómoly.

Fig. 5. *Ditula angustiorana* (Haworth, 1811) (drawing by Csaba Szabóky)

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